

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

RESEARCH PARTICIPATION CONSENT

This work aims to observe how software engineering practices have been adopted in the scenario of Brazilian startups software.

Your participation in this study is voluntary and all data will be anonymized. However, the greater the participation, the more significant the results and contributions of this work will be to the Software Engineering Community.

The questionnaire consists of two stages: The first consists of characterizing the participant, details about the startup, and about the development of the startup's product (s). The estimated average completion time is 10 minutes; The second stage includes questions related to the Software Engineering practices that are adopted by startups. The estimated average completion time is 15 minutes.

This study adopts the ethical and scientific principles that guide scientific research in Experimental Software Engineering. In this way, personal and sensitive data are not requested. All results will be presented in an aggregated form, without the possibility of identifying the respondent.

If you have any questions or suggestions, please contact renatamss@ufba.br.

1. Do you agree to participate in this research?

- Yes
- Not

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE PARTICIPANT

In this section, you will be asked to answer questions about your role at the startup.

2. Do you work at a startup?

- Yes
- Not

3. Do you work on the startup's software development team?

- Yes
- Not

4. Which option describes your relationship with the startup more precisely?

- I am a founder of the startup
- I'm a startup investor
- I am hired by the startup (or provide services)
- This startup is part of a research project
- Other (specify)

5. How long have you been working at this startup?

Up to 1 year

Between 2 to 3 years

Between 4 to 5 years

Between 6 to 10 years

More than 10 years

6. Which option most accurately describes your position at the startup?

Chief of Executive Officer (CEO)

Business Manager

Project manager

Product manager

Chief of Technical Officer (CTO) or Technical Leader

Team leader

Requirements Engineer

Software architect

Software Engineer

Developer / Programmer

Software Test Engineer

User Interface Designer

Researcher

Other (specify)

7. What is your weekly workload?

20 hours a week

50 hours per week

30 hours a week

60 hours per week

40 hours a week

Other (specify)

8. What is your level of education?

Technical / High school completed

Complete postgraduate (master's)

Full graduation

Complete post-graduation (doctorate)

Complete graduate (specialization)

Other (specify)

9. What is the course of your most recent academic education?

Computer science

Information systems

Computer engineering

Electrical engineering
Other (specify)

10. What is your experience, in years of work, with software projects?

- Up to 1 year
- Between 6 to 10 years
- Between 2 to 3 years
- More than 10 years
- Between 4 to 5 years

11. Regarding your experience in software development, which category do you most fit:

- Junior
- Full
- Senior
- Do not know
- Other (specify)

12. What is your age group?

- 18-25 years
- 26-35 years
- 36-45 years
- Over 45 years

13. What is your gender?

- Male
- Feminine
- Other (specify)

14. What is the startup's market?

- Agribusiness
- Communication and Media
- Education
- Entertainment
- E-Commerce
- Finances
- Government
- Logistics and Urban Mobility
- Medicine
- Telecommunications
- Other (specify)

STARTUP CHARACTERIZATION

In this section, you will answer questions related to the startup in which you operate.

15. What is the startup's foundation year?

16. How many customers does the startup have?

1 customer

2-10 customers

11-100 customers

101-1000 customers

More than 1000 customers

17. What is the average annual revenue of the startup in which you operate?

Less than R \$ 81 thousand

Greater than R \$ 81 thousand and less than or equal to R \$ 360 thousand Greater than R \$ 360 thousand and less than or equal to R \$ 4.8 million

Greater than R \$ 4.8 million and less than or equal to R \$ 300 million

Greater than R \$ 300 million

Do not know

18. How big is your organization, in number of employees?

Between 1 and 5 employees

Between 6 and 10 employees

More than 100 employees

Between 11 and 50 employees

Between 51 and 100 employees

19. In which startup ecosystems does your startup belong?

153 Valley - Gurupi / TO

ABC Valley - São Paulo / SP

Açaí Valley - Belém / PA

All Saints Bay - Salvador / BA

Alto Tietê Valley - São Paulo / SP

Aquiri Valley - Rio Branco / AC

Araribóia Valley - Niterói / RJ

Buriti Valley - Boa Vista / RR

Bruto Valley - Barretos / SP

Caju Valley - Aracaju / SE

Cajuína Valley - Teresina / PI

Campinas Startups - Campinas / SP

Campos Valley - Ponta Grossa / PR

Cariocas - Rio de Janeiro / RJ

Carnaúba Valley - Parnaíba / PI

Carranca Valley - Petrolina / PE

Chambery Valley - Araguaína / TO

Blumenau Community - Blumenau / SC
Brasília Community - Brasília / DF
João Pessoa Community - João Pessoa / PB
Quixadá Community - Quixadá / CE
Campos Community - Campos dos Goytacazes / RJ
Criciúma Community - Criciúma / SC
Foz do Iguaçu Community - Foz do Iguaçu / PR
Jataí Community - Jataí / GO
Ji-Paraná Community - Ji-Paraná / RO
Community Ribeirão Preto - Ribeirão Preto / SP
Sobral Community - Sobral / CE
Sorocaba Community - Sorocaba / SP
CommunityRS - Porto Alegre / RS
CommunityRS #Serra - Caxias do Sul / RS
CommunityRS #Pelotas - Pelotas / RS
CommunityRS #SantaMaria - Santa Maria / RS
CommunityRS # TaquariValley - Lajedo / RS
CommunityRS # ValeDosSinos - Canoas / RS
Costa Valley - Balneário Camboriú / SC
Desbravalley - Chapecó / SC
Capixaba Ecosystem - Vitória / ES
HubNorte - Sinop / MT
Iguassu Valley - Cascavel / PR
Jerimum Valley - Natal / RN
JoinvilleStartups - Joinville / SC
Jaraqui Valley - Manaus / AM
Kariri Valley - Juazeiro do Norte / CE
Libertas Valley - Itaúna / MG
Manguez.al - Recife / PE
Parahyba Valley - São José dos Campos / SP
Rapadura Valley - Fortaleza / CE
RedFoot Maringá - Maringá / PR
RedFoot Londrina - Londrina / PR
RioSul Valley - Volta Redonda / RJ
Sandwich Valley - Bauru / SP
San Pedro Valley - Belo Horizonte / MG
SancaHub - São Carlos / SP
Santa Helena Valley - Sete Lagoas / MG
Santana Valley - Feira de Santana / BA
Sete Colinas - Garanhuns / PE
SoLuiíses - São Luiz / MA
Sudo Valley - Pato Branco / PR
Sururu Valley - Maceió / AL
Starttroleiros - Campina Grande / PB
StartupGO - Goiânia / GO

Startup Tocantins - Palmas / TO
StartupMS - Campo Grande / MS
StartupMT - Cuiabá / MT
StartupSC - Florianópolis / SC
Tambaki Valley - Porto Velho / RO
Tucuju Valley - Macapá / AP
UberHub - Uberlândia / MG
Electronics Valley - Santa Rita do Sapucaí / MG
Knowledge Valley - Itabira / MG
Pinhão Valley - Curitiba / PR
Valin Vale dos Inconfidentes - Ouro Preto / MG
ZebuValley - Uberaba / MG
ZeroOnze - São Paulo / SP
Zero40 - Juiz de Fora / MG
Do not know
Not applicable
Other (specify)

20. How many people are on the software development team?

Between 1 and 5 people
Between 6 and 10 people
Between 11 and 50 people
Between 51 and 100 people
More than 100 people

21. What are the functions performed by these people?

Project manager
Software Test Engineer
Chief of Technical Officer (CTO)
User Interface Designer
Requirements Engineer
Researcher
Software architect
Product Owner
Software engineer
Scrum Master
Other (specify)

22. As for receiving financial investment, your startup:

It has received financial investment in the past, but today it is no longer dependent on these contributions
Usually receives investment on a regular basis, as it depends mostly on these contributions
Never received financial investment
Other (specify)

PRODUCT CHARACTERIZATION

In this section, you will answer questions about the product developed by the startup.

23. Which option below best characterizes the startup you work for?

- Software product
- Software and hardware product
- Software as a Service
- Other (specify)

24. In the startup you work for, what is the orientation of the product or service by target audience?

- B2B (Business to Business)
- P2P (Peer to Peer)
- B2C (Business to Consumer)
- B2S (Business to Startup)
- B2B2C (Business to Business to Consumer)
- B2G (Business to Government)
- Other (specify)

25. In the startup you work for, is the software product or service focused on innovation?

- Yes
- Not
- Do not know
- Other (specify)

26. How many software products does the startup you operate currently develop?

27. How long did it take to release the first release of the startup's most important product?

- Within 1 week
- Between 1 and 4 weeks
- Between 2 and 3 months
- Between 4 and 6 months
- Between 6 months and 1 year
- More than 1 year
- Other (specify)

28. Briefly describe this product.

29. In relation to this product / service, has the startup performed any pivots over time?

(A pivot aims to test a fundamental hypothesis about a product or service. It is a change of direction. It is a decision that leads to significantly change one or more of its basic components, but not all: product, entrepreneurial team, business model or growth strategy.)

- Yes (the product was pivoted)
- Not
- Do not know

30. Describe the motivation for pivoting this product.

3 1. How long has the startup development team been working on this product or service?

- At least 1 year
- At least 3 years
- At least 5 years
- At least 10 years, inclusive
- For over 10 years

3 2. What is the stage of the product?

- A product prototype has been developed and has not yet been launched on the market
- Product was launched on the market and is actively developed further with the input of the customer
- Product is quite stable, the focus is on obtaining a customer base
- Product is stable, size, market share and growth rate are established. The focus is on launching new product variations.
- Other (specify)

GENERAL

33. About the Software Engineering processes adopted by the startup, choose the option that best fits each of the following options:

	Formal	Informal	Not applicable
Business Modeling			
Requirements Engineering			
Software Analysis and Design			
Software development			
Software Testing			
Configuration Management			
Environment Management			
Project management			

REQUIREMENTS

Requirements engineering is a set of practices that helps you discover what customers need.

34. At the startup where you work, at what point does the requirement elicitation occur?

- In the initial phase of the project
- At the first meeting with the client

After the customer meeting
At the product / service design meeting
At the beginning of each iteration of software development
Not applicable
Other (specify)

35. What method (s) of eliciting / extracting requirements is (are) used in the startup?

Ethnography
Workshop
Prototyping
Interviews
Questionnaires
Brainstorming
JAD (Joint Application Design)
Not applicable
Other (specify)

36. Choose the tools used to prototype the product / service

Adobe XD
OmniGraffle
Axure
Origami
Balsamiq Mockups
Pencil
Codeqa
Pidoco
Fluid
Pixate
In Vision
Proto.io
JustInMind
Sketch
Marvel
UXPin
Moqups
WebFlow
MockFlow
Zeplin
Ninja Mock
Other (specify)

37. What phases of the requirements engineering process at the startup you work in?

Requirements elicitation
Requirements specification
Elaboration of requirements

Requirements validation
Requirements negotiation
Requirements management
Other (specify)

38. In the startup you work for, is the customer involved in eliciting requirements?

Yes
Not
Do not know

39. How are the requirements documented at the startup?

Wireframe
Paper prototyping
Mockups
Document containing description in natural language of requirements
Not applicable
Other (specify)

40. Describe how the requirements are documented.

41. When there is a change or request to add new requirements, is the documentation usually updated?

Yes
Not
Do not know

42. What tools are used to document and manage requirements?

Accompa
IRIS Business Architect
aNimble
Jama Software
Atlassian JIRA
Modern Requirements Tool Suite
Aligned elements
Orcans
Borland Caliber
Process Street
Case Complete
ReqTest
Cause-Effect Modeling Suite
ReqSuite ® RM
Enterprise Architect
SpiraTeam by Inflectra
FogBugz
Visure Requirements

Helix RM
ReQtest
IBM Rational DOORS
Xebrio
Innoslate
Not applicable
Other (specify)

43. What quality attributes are observed in the products / services developed?

Legal aspects
Solution price
Business rules
Portability
Compatibility (with other versions and migration needs)
Installation requirements
Reusability
Reliability
Robustness
Performance
Support
Documentation
Usability
Flexibility
Use of patterns
Target hardware and software
Testability
Integrity / security
Fault tolerance
Interoperability
Volume of use
Internationalization
Not applicable
Maintainability
Packaging
Other (specify)

* 44. How is the scope of the minimum viable product (MVP) defined?

Brainstorming
Backlog prioritization
Use case prioritization
Customer prioritization
History-based
Specialists
Not applicable

SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The process of defining the software architecture is a process of defining its components, interfaces and other characteristics.

45. What tools are used to document the architecture?

Archi
Papyrus
Diagrams
StarUML
Enterprise Architect
UML Designer
Modelio
WhiteStartUML
NClass
Not applicable
Other (specify)

46. What architectural patterns are commonly used in startup projects?

Batch
Model-View-Controller (MVC)
Blackboard
Peer-to-peer
Broker
Presentation-Abstraction-Control (PAC)
Layers
Pipe-filter
Client-Server
Process control
Event-bus
Reflection
Interpreter
Rule-based
Master-slave
Microkernel
Not applicable

47. Does the startup's software architecture project usually follow any reuse approach?

Configurable Vertical Applications
Architecture Patterns
Program Libraries
Design Patterns
Legacy Systems Packaging
Reuse of COTS Products
Model-driven engineering
ERP Systems

Application Framework
Service-oriented systems
Program Generators
Software Product Line
Not applicable
Other (specify)

INTERFACE DESIGN

Interface design is an activity that must guarantee the interaction between the user and the machine, providing effective operation.

48. What does the startup look for with the UI design activity?

Accessibility
Recovery
Consistency
Usability
Easy learning
Utility
Easy memorization
Do not know
Familiarity
Not applicable
Other (specify)

49. How are product / service user interface designs created?

Customer participation / collaboration
Prototypes
User participation / collaboration
Wireframes
Analysis of similar applications
Other (specify)

50. Which (ais) time (s) the client is involved in defining the application interface design?

At the first application design definition meeting
During prototyping
Before product release
During training for product delivery
On product delivery
Never
Do not know
Other (specify)

DEVELOPMENT

Software development refers to the detailed creation of work software through a combination of coding, verification, unit testing, integration testing and debugging.

51. What programming languages are commonly used in startup software projects?

Ç

Objective-C

C ++

Perl

Ç#

PHP

Dart

Python

F #

R

Go

Ruby

Haskell

Rust

Java

Swift

JavaScript

TypeScript

Moon

VB.NET

Other (specify)

52. What development platforms are used in the startup's software projects?

Android Studio

Unity

Atom

R Studio

Eclipse

RadStudio

JetBrains

Visual Studio

NetBeans

XCode

PyCharm

Other (specify)

TEST

The software test consists of the dynamic verification that a program provides expected behaviors in a finite set of test cases, properly selected in the generally infinite execution domain.

53. At startup, how are tests performed on the software product / service?

Manually
Automatically
Tests are not performed
Other (specify)

54. Who tests the startup's software product / service?

An independent testing team
The development team itself
Only unit tests are performed by the developer himself
Testing is performed by a developer who was not involved in coding
Customer tests the product
No one runs a test
Other (specify)

55. What tools for defect management and change requests are used in the startup?

BugZilla
OTRS
Eventum
Redmine
Fossil
Trac
Github
WebIssues
Mantis BT
Not applicable
Other (specify)

56. What test execution tools are used in the startup?

Ranorex
CrossBrowserTesting
TestComplete
Testimony
QMetry Automation Studio
ZeuZ Test Automation Framework
LEAPWORK
Selenium
Experitest
Subject7
Katalon Studio
Appium
Testsigma
Micro Focus UFT
LambdaTest
Test Studio
Qualibrate

IBM Rational Functional Tester
Worksoft
Not applicable
Other (specify)

57. What test management tools are used in the startup?

aqua
SPIRATEST by Inflectra
Kualitee
Test Collab
qTest
TestFLO for JIRA
QACoverage
TestMonitor
JIRA
Testpad
JunoOne
TestRail
Klaros-Testmanagement
XQual
PractiTest
Xray - Cutting Edge Test Management
ReQtest
Zephyr
Requirements and Test Management for Jira (RTM)
Not applicable
Other (specify)

* 58. What levels of testing does the product / service undergo?

Unit testing
Acceptance test
Component testing
Integration test
System testing
none
Do not know

59. Does the startup apply any techniques for testing?

Equivalence partitioning
Limit value analysis
Decision table testing
State transition test
Use-case testing
Coverage test and instruction
Decision testing and coverage

Assumption of error
Exploratory testing
Decision testing
Coverage test
Checklist-based testing
ad hoc
Other (specify)
None of the above
Do not know

60. What is the purpose of testing the software?

Acceptance test
Usability and Human-Computer Interaction Testing
Installation test
Back-to-back tests
Alpha / beta test
Recovery tests
Regression test
Feasibility and Evaluation
Performance test
None of the above
Security testing
Do not know
Stress test
Other (specify)

61. How often does the startup release a test release?

1-2 days
3-4 weeks
3-7 days
2-3 months
1-2 weeks
more than 3 months
Other (specify)

62. How often does the startup release a release to the customer?

1-2 days
3-7 days
1-2 weeks
3-4 weeks
2-3 months
more than 3 months

63. When does the software testing activity begin?
When eliciting requirements
At the end of coding, before delivering to the customer
When the application architecture is being defined
The customer even tests
When coding
Other (specify)

MAINTENANCE

Software maintenance aims to modify existing software, preserving its integrity.

64. What maintenance techniques does the startup adopt?
Understanding the program
Reengineering
reverse engineering
Migration
Product discontinuation
Not applicable
Other (specify)
65. What configuration management tools (eg versioning, baseline) does the startup use?
Bitbucket Server
Team Foundation Server (TFS)
Subversion
Kallithea
Mercurial
Helix Core Version Control
GIT
GitLab
Not applicable
Other (specify)
66. Does the startup produce any documentation to support configuration management?
Yes
Not
Do not know
67. How much does the average time to launch a version / release of the product / service?
1-2 days
3-7 days
1-2 weeks
3-4 weeks
1-3 months

3-6 months

More than 6 months

68. In the startup in which you operate, does the pressure for the release of the product / service come from which one (s) are interested?

Client

User

Investor

Market

Not applicable

Other (specify)

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management can be defined as the application of management activities - planning, coordination, measurement, monitoring, control and reporting - to ensure that software products and software engineering services are provided in an efficient, effective manner and for the benefit of interested parties.

69. In the startup you work for, which feasibility analysis (s) is (are) performed?

Technical viability

Market viability

Economic viability

Not applicable

Do not know

Other (specify)

70. Which of the following steps are part of the startup's planning activities?

Process planning

Resource allocation

Delivery planning

Risk management

Effort

Quality management

Schedule

Management plan

Estimates

Not applicable

Other (specify)

71. What metrics are collected in the startup's projects?

Project metrics

Product metrics

Customer satisfaction metrics

Not applicable

Other (specify)

72. What tools does the startup use to collect / manage metrics?

Analyst4j
Loc Metric
Code Counter
Soure Monitor
Code Analyzer
Eclipse Metric Plug -in
Do not know
Not applicable
Other (specify)

73. What tools are used by the startup to support the project management process?

ActiveCollab
Podium
Asana
ProofHub
Basecamp
Teamwork Projects
ClickUp
Trello
dotProject
Workzone
JIRA
Wrike
MeisterTask
Zoho Projects
Monday
Not applicable
Microsoft Project
Other (specify)

DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

A software development process consists of a set of interrelated activities that transform one or more inputs into outputs while consuming resources to carry out the transformation.

74. Which development process approach best characterizes the one used by your startup?

ad hoc
Iterative
Waterfall
Agile
Clean room
Do not know
Other (specify)

75. What agile practices does the startup follow?

3C's

Incremental Development

Story Splitting

Automated Build

INVEST

Story Mapping

ATDD Acceptance Tests

Iterative Development

Scrum of Scrum

Backlog

Iterations

Sign Up

Backroom Grooming

Kanban Board

Simple Design

BDD

Lead Time

Sustainable Pace

Burndown Chart

Mock Objects

Task Board

Collective Ownership

Niko-Niko

Team

Continuous Integration

Pair Programming

Team Room

Continuous Deployment

Personas

Three Questions

CRC Cards

Planning Poker

Timebox

Daily Meeting

Point Estimation

TDD

Definition of Done

Project Charts

Ubiquitous Language

Definition of Ready

Quick Design Session

Unit Tests

Exploratory Testing

Relative Estimation
Usability Testing
Facilitation
Refactoring
Users Stories
Frequent Release
Role Feature
Velocity
Given-When-Then
Rules of Simplicity
Version control
Heartbeat Retrospective
Simple Design
Not applicable
Other (specify)

76. How do you plan the software development activities?

Planning and activities are done by the project manager.

The project manager defines the development activities, and each member of the team develops a specific activity according to affinity and aptitude.

The software development team is self-managing.

Other (specify)

There is no systematization of software development activities.

Do not know

Not applicable

Closure

77. Thank you for your availability! If you are interested in receiving the results of this survey, please provide the email address in the field below.